

Chemometric expertise of the ecotoxicity/physicochemical features links of silver nanoparticles - environmental aspects

Miroslava A. Nedyalkova¹, Borjana V. Donkova, Vasil D. Simeonov

University of Sofia, Faculty of chemistry and pharmacy, 1 J. Bourchier Av., 1164 Sofia, Bulgaria

Abstract

Ecotoxicological aspects of nanomaterials in the aquatic environment are still scarcely studied. Given the growing variety of nanoparticles (NP), along with the diversity of aquatic species and environments, a key to promote sound risk assessment in nanoecotoxicology is to understand the mechanisms that govern the fate of NP in aquatic environments and their behaviour at the NP- biota interface. This paper points to collect and discuss data on ecotoxicological effects observed in aquatic species and to analyse them on a multivariate statistical view. Herein, we expand the knowledge of environmental impact of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs), testing the acute toxicity of 47 AgNP on crustacean organisms eukaryotic (*D.Magna*, *T. platyurus* *D. galeata*). Physicochemical properties, stabilisation agents, toxicological endpoints and test media were monitored as adding outcome factors for evaluation of environmental effects due to exposure to nanoparticles. The chemometric expertise performed by the use of hierarchical, non-hierarchical cluster analysis and principal components analysis revealed specific links between the ecotoxicological and physicochemical features of the nanoparticles and helped in creating specific patterns of nanoparticles discriminated either by ecotoxicity or by physicochemical parameters.

Key words: silver nanoparticles, ecotoxicity, physicochemical parameters, multivariate statistics

¹ Corresponding author's email: mici345@yahoo.com

Silver nanoparticles (Ag-NPs) have recently been the goal of intense research because of the potential hazard they pose to humans and other biological organisms (1–9). Definitely, the silver nanoparticles toxicity to a variety of organisms has been established in a numeral of studies. The toxicity has been perceived for aquatic algae (10, 11), and fungi (4), vertebrates (zebra fish) (12), microorganisms (*Escherichia coli*, (13,14) *Pseudomonas putida* (15)), and human cells (skin keratinocytes, lung fibroblast cells, and glioblastoma cells) (16,17).

The list of studies showing the negative impact of Ag-NPs on the environment and possibly on humans is readily discussed (1–9).

The toxicity of Ag-NPs is partly explained by the release of Ag ions; it remains unclear if Ag-NPs are a direct cause of enhanced toxicity. For example, Navarro et al. (10) presented evidence that toxicity is mainly the result of Ag ions and that Ag-NPs contribute to toxicity as a source of dissolved Ag ions.

It is interesting to focus on the results, which prove the hypothesis of toxicity that increase with decreased particle size, regarding to the experimental data. We have a vast number of data showing that smaller NPs were less toxic or, of no size-dependent toxicity. One reason for these contradictory data could be that the NPs used for the toxicity tests are not usually monodisperse so theoretically, causing toxic effects of different magnitude. Due to the lack of systematic experimental data on size-specific toxic effects and contradictory experimental results obtained so far, it is not surprising that there is no clear understanding of the effects of particle size or we can talk in general about physiochemistry parameters effects on toxicity and ecotoxicity (18). Consequently, nanoparticle (NP) size has not been involved as an important parameter in toxicity prediction models (QSAR or QNAR models) (19) and if NP size is bigger than 15–20 nm, it is not considered to be an important variable in determining their biological effects (20, 21). Also, another interesting point being neglected is the aggregation state of Ag-NPs like important factor impacting to the transport and toxicity of these nanomaterials. In this sense, Kvittek et al. (22) established a correlation between

stability against aggregation and the minimum concentration that inhibits the growth of a variety of reference and isolated strains of bacteria. Other studies have demonstrated a clear relation between nanoparticle aggregation and loss of an inhibitory effect on bacterial growth (23). The lack of complete consideration in this area is the difficulty of precisely measuring environmentally induced changes in NP aggregation state. While a variety of techniques for estimating size exist (e.g., dynamic light scattering, DLS; transmission electron microscopy, TEM; atomic force microscopy, AFM;), they all have essential problems, and different techniques must be used to minimise errors. The problems become more complex when the diversity of different media modes containing various combinations of ions for toxicological assays is concerned.

The present study collects and interprets available in the literature data on the ecotoxicity of Ag nanoparticles in aquatic environments depending of physicochemical parameters of the discusses objects. We propose a scheme about the relation ecotoxicity - physicochemical parameters obtained by multivariate statistical analysis.

The major goal of the study is to reveal patterns of similarity (specific relationships) between the different nanoparticle systems, on one hand, and between the estimators, on the other. There are many studies dealing with relationship between particle size parameters and particle properties but quite few using ecotoxicity as additional estimator of the nanoparticle properties.

Experimental

Samples

The input data set (Table 1) from several studies on the toxicity of AgNPs, especially to aquatic organisms, with varied coating and sizes were assessed (24-31).

The input data set consists of 47 different nanoparticle systems described by four physicochemical features (primary size *PS* is measured from TEM, AFM images; these methods give the core size of organic coated Ag-NPs ; primary hydrodynamic diameter *PHD*

is the effective diameter of as prepared or suspended in distilled water organic coated Ag-NPs, measured by dynamic light scattering; hydrodynamic diameter in test media $HD-TM$ is the effective diameter of organic coated Ag-NPs in the test medium; zeta (ζ) potential in test media ZP [mV] is the surface charge, indicating the degree of repulsion between the nanoparticles against aggregation and acute ecotoxicity measure AT presented as value of EC_{50} or LC_{50} is the acute toxicity measured on crustacean eukaryotic organisms.

In Table 1 the input data set with dimension [47x5] is presented where 47 nanoparticle systems are described by 5 features (ecotoxicity and four physicochemical parameters). The set seems appropriate for multivariate statistical treatment. The data mining uses principal components analysis and non-hierarchical cluster analysis (K-nearest neighbor method) for data modelling and interpretation.

Ag-NPs suspensions used in toxicity testing were characterised through a combination of atomic force or electron microscopy (AFM, TEM, SEM), dynamic light scattering (DLS) and Doppler electrophoresis to determine particle size, hydrodynamic diameter, aggregation state, and ζ potentials.

The physicochemical parameters and toxicity were measured at different Ag-NPs concentration using different kind of both preparation methodology and method (i.e. shaking of suspension or mixing and/or sonification and filtration and etc., TEM or DLS). The acute toxicities of the AgNPs suspensions to different kind of crustacean (mainly *Daphnia magna* and *Thamnocephalus platyurus*) were performed using conventional OECD or U.S. EPA test procedures. All measurements were done by authors of source articles.

Table 1 The input data set for Ag-NPs based on literature data.

Chemometric Analysis

Chemometric analysis was performed testing different statistical approaches as possible responsible of the observed inconsistency reported by the literature data collected in this paper. Basically, several groups of such methods could be defined (32, 33).

Chemometric or Exploratory data analysis (EDA) is based mainly on the multivariate statistical methods. One of the major method is called principal components analysis (PCA) or factor analysis (FA). Using these methods one could visualise a multivariate data set, to detect relationships in a reduced coordinate space both between object of interest and variable characterising the objects.

Another group of methods are often named unsupervised pattern recognition. Cluster analysis (also PCA) is one of the mostly applied from this group. Its goals are to construct a scheme of similarities between different features, called dendrogram, in which more closely related objects are closer to each other. The main branches of the tree-like scheme represent deviations from the similarities. Unsupervised pattern recognition differs from exploratory data analysis in that the aim of the method is to detect similarities whereas using EDA there no particular insight whether at all or how many groups will be detected. Very often it is said that the unsupervised pattern recognition is a spontaneous classification method without any preliminary training of the data set to follow a specific requirement to classify the data into a preliminary chosen number of similarity groups.

Principal components analysis (PCA)

Principal component analysis (PCA) seems to be the most widespread multivariate chemometric technique and is a typical display method (also known as *eigenvector analysis*, *eigenvector decomposition* or *Karhunen-Loève expansion*). It enables revealing the “hidden” structure of the data set and helps to explain the influence of latent factors on the data distribution. PCA is done on covariance matrix when the data are centered or on correlation matrix when the data are standardized. PCA transforms the original data matrix into a product of two matrices, one of which contains the information about the objects or cases (e.g. sampling sites from a monitoring net) and the other about the features (e.g. chemical or physicochemical parameters determining the quality of the environmental system in concentration units).

Interpretation of the results of PCA is usually carried out by visualization of the component scores and loadings. In the score plot, the linear projection of objects is found, representing the main part of the total variance of the data (in the plot PC1 vs. PC2). Other projection plots are also available (e.g. PC1 vs. PC3 or PC2 vs. PC3) but they represent less percentage of explained total variance of the system in consideration. Correlation and importance of feature variables is to be decided from the factor loadings plots.

Cluster Analysis

Cluster analysis (CA) is a well developed tool for solving classification problems, based on unsupervised learning. CA enables objects stepwise aggregation according to the similarity of their features. As a result hierarchically or non-hierarchically ordered clusters are formed. A single cluster describes a group of objects that are more similar to each other than to objects outside the group.

In case of CA one task is related with determination of similarity between measured objects, but equally, important task is to define how objects or clusters are combined at each step of similarity assessment procedure. One possibility for clustering objects is their hierarchical aggregation. In this case, the objects are combined according to their distances from or similarities to each other. Within hierarchical aggregation, agglomerative and divisive methods can be distinguished. Divisive clustering is based on splitting the whole set of objects into individual clusters, while in case of more frequently used agglomerative clustering one starts with single objects and gradually merges them in broader groups. Usually, some objects create one broader group, while rest of them creates the other. As in case of distance measure various algorithms (linkage techniques) are available to decide on the number of clusters.

The algorithms for non – hierarchical clustering offer the division of the studied objects into *a priori* given number of clusters (determined by some practical or theoretical reasons).

Chemometric tools have been frequently applied from analytical and pharmaceutical method optimization problems and environmental issues to spectroscopy data analysis. The use of chemometrics for the treatment of different data sets provides a valuable tool for objective decision-making (34-38).

All statistical analyses were carried out using STATISTICA 8.0 statistical software.

Results and discussion

The input data set was standardised by z-transform procedure in order to eliminate the parameter dimension impact on the classification and interpretation results. As already mentioned, one of the aims of the study was to find relationships between the features used for description of the nanoparticle systems. Principal components analysis (PCA) was carried out searching for similarity between features (factor loadings consideration). Two latent factors were identified which explain over 70 % of the total variance (the explained variance by PC 1 is 49.2 % and by PC 2 – 22.4%). In Fig. 1 the biplot PC 1 vs. PC 2 is presented giving a reliable explanation between the features.

As seen there is a close similarity between three of the physicochemical parameters (PS, PHD and HD-TM) which have high factor loadings on PC1. It confirms that these three parameters simultaneously are responsible for the structural identity of the nanoparticle systems in consideration and could be (again simultaneously) a discriminating factor for every single nanoparticle composition.

Fig. 1 PC1 vs. PC 2 biplot for similarity between the nanoparticle features

The acute toxicity and the zeta- ζ potential are negatively correlated with high factor loadings on PC 2. It means that these two estimators are different as discriminating factors for the nanoparticle compositions studied. In the next stage of the multivariate statistical analysis, non-hierarchical cluster analysis (known as K-nearest neighbor method) was applied to reveal specific patterns of similarity between the nanocomposites. Four clusters were identified as follows:

K1 (10, 11, 13)

K2 (21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 30, 31, 32, 39, 40, 41, 45, 46, 47)

K3 (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 12, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 34, 35, 20, 43, 44)

K4 (9, 26, 27, 28, 29, 33, 36, 37, 38, 42)

The non-hierarchical clustering in preliminary indicated groups was proven by carrying out hierarchical clustering of the same data set using squared Euclidean distances as

similarity measure, Ward's method of linkage and Sneath's criterion of cluster significance. The hierarchical dendrogram is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Hierarchical dendrogram for clustering of 47 nanoparticle systems

It could be easily seen that the marked clusters on the dendrogram have the same content as those identified by non-hierarchical approach. It proves that the separation into four groups of similarity is stable and reliable. It is important to understand which the discriminating features responsible for the cluster formation are. In Fig. 3 the average values for each feature and for each of the identified four clusters are presented.

Fig. 3 Average values of features for each cluster

Cluster 1 collects the only three objects - two uncoated commercial and coffee-coated Ag-NPs. This cluster is characterised by highest average values for the particle size features (it includes the biggest particles with respect to the initial size and DLS). At the same time, it indicates lowest (based on multivariate statistical methods) average acute toxicity and relatively low average zeta- ζ potential. The relative little number of objects in this cluster allow some preliminary conclusions to be made below.

Cluster 2 and **Cluster 3** have the same average primary sizes of Ag-NPs, which are lowest between all clusters. The average HD-TM and average toxicity of these clusters are very similar. The separation is due to the zeta- ζ potential value: **Cluster 2** shows the highest average zeta- ζ potential for all clusters, while **Cluster 3** shows lowest average zeta- ζ potential.

Cluster 4 collects the objects, very similar to that included in Cluster 3 with respect to the physicochemical parameters (the same average HD-TM, relatively low zeta- ζ potential, bigger only with 10 nm in average size Ag higher -NPs). However, **Cluster 4** reveals **highest** average toxicity between all clusters (a magnitude higher than that of Cluster 3 and 2).

The setting up of objects in clusters 2, 3 and 4 based on cluster analysis can be correlated with experimental results of Binova et al. (27). The reported results are for the toxicity of PVP-coated Ag NPs and colargol (protein coated nanosilver) tested to *Daphnia magna* and *Thamnocephalus platyurus* in artificial freshwater and in five kinds of natural

waters. The PVP-coated particles have higher zeta potential (-4.86 mV) than protein coated nanosilver (-16.5 mV). The first are included in Cluster 2 despite of the type of crustacean organisms (except one sample, belonging to Cluster 4 due to its different toxicity), while the second, tested with *D.magna*, and are included in Cluster 3. The same protein coated colloidal silver, tested to *T. platyurus* in different media, however, belongs to Cluster 4.

Conclusion

In summary, our paper reports the chemometrics interpretation of data set based on literature data for physicochemical and ecotoxicity features of Ag-NPs. Statistical methods reveal four specific patterns of Ag-NPs discriminated by physicochemical parameters and ecotoxicity levels. In this paper, we describe how our chemometric expertise was used in developing the relation ecotoxicity/physicochemical features. It become evident that three clusters (2, 3, and 4) are actually equal with respect to the sizes (primary and diameter). Cluster 2, however, shows the highest average zeta potential at a relatively higher acute toxicity as compared to clusters 1 and 3. Cluster 4 is characterised by highest average acute toxicity.

On the base of the concrete approach, we can conclude that the discrepancy of interpretation the linkage between ecotoxicity/physicochemical features could be diminished. Such an approach allows to predict the ecotoxicity patterns tested in different media of Ag-NPs having different size, coating, and stability.

An important outcome of the present study is that NPs of high toxicity have been identified by chemometric expertise. Probably, higher toxicity could be linked to the specific dimensions of some physicochemical features. It seems obvious that large NPs (cluster 1) are of low toxicity, since the penetration to organism is not so easy as in case of smaller particles. The NPs included in cluster 2, which are characterized by high zeta potential, are more toxic because of the lower potential needed for coagulation. Probably, these NPs

remain in the state of ease to penetrate cells. The higher toxicity of the NPs included in cluster 4 could be related to the small dimensions of the nanoparticles included in the cluster.

Acknowledgments

The support of H2020 program of the European Union (project Materials Networking) is gratefully acknowledged

References

- (1) Ratte, H.T. (1999) *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* **18**, 89–108.
- (2) Quadros, M.E., & Marr, L.C. (2010) *J. Air Waste Manage. Assoc.* **60**, 770–781.
- (3) Panyala, N.R. Pena-Mendez, E.M., & Havel, J. (2008) *J. Appl. Biomed.* **6**, 117–129.
- (4) Navarro, E., Baun, A., Behra, R., Hartmann, N.B., Filser, J., Miao, A.J., Quigg, A., Santschi, P.H., & Sigg, L. (2008) *Ecotoxicology* **17**, 372–386.
- (5) Marambio-Jones, C., & Hoek, E.M.V. (2010) *J. Nanopart. Res.* **12**, 1531–1551.
- (6) Luoma, S.N. (2008) *Silver nanotechnologies and the environment: old problems or new challenges*, Woodrow Wilson International Center for Scholars, Washington, DC..
- (7) Klaine, S.J., Alvarez, P.J.J., Batley, G.E., Fernandes, T.F., Handy, R.D., Lyon, D.Y., Mahendra, S., McLaughlin, M.J., & Lead, J.R. (2008) *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* **27**, 1825–1851.
- (8) Khaydarov, R. R., Khaydarov, R.A., Estrin, Y., Evgrafova, S., Scheper, T., Endres, C., & Cho, S.Y. (2009) in *NATO Science for Peace and Security Series C: Environmental Security*, I. Linkov & J. Steevens (Eds), Shpringer-Verlag, pp 287–297.

- (9) Ghaedi, M., Shokrollahi, A., Niknam, K., Niknam, E., Derki, S., & Soylak, M. (2009) *J. AOAC Int.* **92**, 907–913.
- (10) Navarro, E., Piccapietra, F., Wagner, B., Marconi, F., Kaegi, R., Odzak, N. Sigg, L., & Behra, R. (2008) *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **42**, 8959–8964.
- (11) Gubbins, E.J., Batty, L.C., & Lead, J.R. (2011) *Environ. Pollut.* **159**, 1551–1559.
- (12) Asharani, P.V., Wu, Y.L., Gong, Z., & Valiyaveetil, S. (2008) *Nanotechnology* **19**, 255102.
- (13) Sondi, I., & Salopek-Sondi, B. (2004) *J. Colloid Interf. Sci.* **275**, 177–182.
- (14) Dror-Ehre, A., Mamane, H., Belenkova, T., Markovich, G., & Adin, A. (2009) *J. Colloid. Interf. Sci.* **339**, 521–526.
- (15) Fabrega, J., Renshaw, J.C., & Lead, J.R. (2009) *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **43**, 9004–9009.
- (16) Lu, W., Senapati, D., Wang, S., Tovmachenko, O., Singh, A.K., Yu, H., & Ray, P.C. (2010) *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **487**, 92–96.
- (17) Asharani, P.V., Mun, G.L.K., Hande, M.P.; & Valiyaveetil, S. (2009) *ACS Nano* **3**, 279–290.
- (18) Bai, Y., Wu, F., White, J.C., & Xing, B. (2014) *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **48**, 3098–3099.
- (19) Ivask, A., Juganson, K., Bondarenko, O., Mortimer, M., Aruoja, V., Kasemets, K., Blinova, I., Heinlaan, M., Slaveykova, V., & Kahru, A. (2014) *Nanotoxicology* **8**, 57-71.
- (20) Burello, E., Worth, A.P. (2011) *WIREs Nanomed. Nanobiotechnol.* **3**, 298–306.
- (21) Puzyn, T., Rasulev, B., Gajewicz, A., Hu, X., Dasari, T.P., Michalkova, A., Hwang, H.M., Toropov, A., Leszczynska, D., & Leszczynski, J. (2011) *Nat Nano* **6**, 175–178.

- (22) Kvitek, L., Panacek, A., Soukupova, J., Kolar, M., Vecerova, R.; Pucek, R., Holecova, M., & Zboril, R. (2008) *J. Phys. Chem. C* **112**, 5825–5834.
- (23) Lok, C.N., Ho, C.M., Chen, R., He, Q.Y., Yu, W.Y., Sun, H., Tam, P.K.H., Chiu, J.F., & Che, C.M. (2007) *J. Biol. Inorg. Chem.* **12**, 527–534
- (24) Li, T., Albee, B., Alemayehu, M., Diaz, R., Ingham, L., Kamal, S., Rodriguez, M., & Bishnoi, S. W. (2010) *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* **398**, 689–700.
- (25) Allen, H.J., Impellitteri, C.A., Macke, D.A., Heckman, J.L., Poynton, H.C., Lazorchak, J.M., Govindaswamy, S., Roose, D.L., & Nadagouda, M.N. (2010) *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* **29**, 2742–2750
- (26) Cunningham, S., Brennan-Fournet, M. E., Ledwith, D., Byrnes, L., & Joshi, L. (2013) *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **47**, 3883–3892
- (27) Blinova, I., Niskanen, J., Kajankari, P., Kanarbik, L., Kaekinen, A., Tenhu, H., Penttinen, O., & Kahru, A. (2013) *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* **20**, 3456–3463
- (28) Ivask, A., Kurvet, I., Kasemets, K., Blinova, I., Aruoja, V., Suppi, S., Vija, H., Kakinen, A., Titma, T., Heinlaan, M., Visnapuu, M., Koller, D., Kisandm, A., & Kahru, A. (2014) *PLOS ONE* **9**, e102108
- (29) Silva, T., Pokhrel, L.R., Dubey, B., Tolaymat, T. M., Maier, K. J., & Liu, X. (2014) *Sci. Total Environ.* **468–469**, 968–976
- (30) Vöelker, C., Boedicker, C., Daubenthaler, J., Oetken, M., & Oehlmann, J. (2013) *PLOS ONE* **8**, e75026
- (31) Zhao, C.M., & Wang, W.X. (2012) *Nanotoxicology* **6**, 361–370
- (32) Massart, D.L., & Kaufman, L. (1983) *The Interpretation of Analytical Chemical Data by the Use of Cluster Analysis*, Wiley-Interscience, New York, NY.

- (33) Massart, D.L., Vandeginste, B.G.M., & Buydens, L.M.C. (1998) *Handbook of Chemometrics and Qualimetrics: Data Handling in Science and Technology*, Parts A and B, Data Handling in Science and Technology, D.L. Massart, B.G.M. Vandeginste, L.M.C. Buydens, S. De Jong, P.J. Lewi & J. Smeyers-Verbeke (Eds), Elsevier, Amsterdam.
- (34) Rueda, A., Samaniego-Sánchez, C., Olall, M., Giménez, R., & Cabrera-Vique, C. (2016) *J. AOAC Int.* **99**, 489-494.
- (35) Hristov, H., Nedyalkova, M., Madurga, S., & Simeonov, V. (2016) *J. Mat. Sci. Technol.*, (in press) ; doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2016.07.016
- (36) Wiczerzak, M., Kudlak, B., Yotova, G., Nedyalkova, M., Tsakovski, S., Simeonov, V., & Namiesnik, J. (2016) *Sci. Total Environ.* **571**, 259-268.
- (37) Bigus, P., Tsakovski, S., Simeonov, V., Namiesnik, J., & Tobiszewski, M. (2016) *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* **408**, 3833-3841.
- (38) Marc, M., Bielawska, M., Simeonov, V., Namiesnik, J., & Zabiegala, B. (2016) *Environ. Res.* **147**, 513-524.

<i>Object</i>	<i>Type of Ag-NPs</i>	<i>Test media</i>	<i>Acute toxicity- test organism/endpoint</i>	<i>References</i>
1 - 6	Laboratory-synthesised citrate coated Ag NPs;	Standard synthetic freshwater (SSF); OECD Guideline for Testing of Chemicals (OECD 1984)	<i>D.Magna</i> ; 48-h LC50	(24)
7-13	Uncoated and citrate coated commercial Ag NPs and laboratory-synthesised Ag NPs (coffee or citrate coated);	Moderately hard reconstituted water; toxicity test according to U.S. EPA	<i>D.Magna</i> ; 48-h LC50	(25,26)

14-25	Commercial protein-coated Ag NPs (collargol) and synthesised PVP-coated Ag NPs (covalently attached via sulfur linkages)	Natural waters and artificial freshwater - ISO medium (OECD 202) for <i>D. magna</i> ,	<i>D.Magna</i> ; 48-h EC50	(27)
26-33		Moderately hard artificial fresh water (US EPA 2005) for <i>T. platyurus</i> ;	<i>T. platyurus</i> ; 24-h LC50	
34-38	Commercial citrate-coated Ag NPs;	Artificial freshwater –AFW (OECD 202) Toxicity test according to OECD 202 guideline.	<i>D.Magna</i> ; 48-h EC50	(28)
39-41	Syntesised Ag NPs - citrate-coated, PVP-coated, and branched polyethyleneimine (BPEI)-coated;	Moderately hard reconstituted water Toxicity test according to USEPA guidelines (USEPA, 1987)	<i>D.Magna</i> ; 48-h LC50	(29)
42-44	Commercial PVP-coated Ag NPs;	Toxicity test according to OECD guidelines for testing of chemicals, no. 202.	<i>D. magna</i> , <i>D. pulex</i> , <i>D. galeata</i> ; 48-h EC50	(30)
45-47	Commercial Ag NPs with different coating- lactate, polyvinylpyrrolidone, and sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonate	Media were simplified M7 (SM7, Samel, et al. 1999) with modified Ca concentration (the same Ca concentration of 20 mg/L as in the brook water)	<i>D.Magna</i> ; 48-h LC50	(31)

Caption:

Table 1 The input data set for Ag-NPs based on literature data.

Caption:

Fig. 1 PC1 vs. PC 2 biplot for similarity between the nanoparticle features

Caption:

Fig. 2 Hierarchical dendrogram for clustering of 47 nanoparticle systems

Caption:

Fig. 3 Average values of features for each cluster